

Finnish Log Construction in Northeast China

Market Overview

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Subject: Management Science and Engineering

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Declaration of Originality

I hereby declare that this dissertation has been composed by myself and has not been presented or accepted in any previous application for a degree. The work, of which this is a record, has been carried out by myself unless otherwise stated, and where the work is mine, it reflects personal views and values. All quotations have been distinguished by quotation marks, and all sources of information have been acknowledged by means of references, including those on the Internet. I agree that the University has the right to submit my work to the plagiarism detection sources for originality checks.

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With gratitude,

Kasper Anttila

In Shenyang, June 14th, 2024

Abstract

This dissertation focuses on the potential for the Finnish log construction industry to expand into Northeast China. It assesses global trends, regional challenges, and opportunities. The study includes a general market overview of the current state of log construction and an exploration of the market through a survey targeting consumers in Northeast China. The survey assesses local awareness, preferences, and attitudes towards Finnish log construction, providing unique insights into market potential and consumer trends. The research addresses logistical, regulatory, and cultural challenges faced by Finnish companies in the region, emphasising the importance of network building, adapting to local regulations, and overcoming the scarcity of wood construction expertise.

The findings suggest that log construction is viewed favourably for its aesthetic and ecological properties beyond a positive brand image. However, critical barriers such as stringent fire safety regulations, limited local expertise, and logistical challenges in raw material procurement are identified. The study proposes potential market scenarios for Finnish log construction, highlighting opportunities in suburban and rural settings, leisure and experience-based developments like ski resorts and holiday villages, and implementing innovative public projects.

This research emphasises the significance of enhancing Finnish log construction exports to Northeast China, noting its distinctiveness due to a scarcity of similar studies. It recommends innovative strategies for log construction adaptation in the Northeast China context, prioritising innovation, collaboration, and an in-depth understanding of local market nuances. Additionally, it recommends a path forward for investigating log construction's complex challenges, underlining the importance of detailed consumer behaviour research, technological advancements, environmental evaluations, and analyses of material costs.

Keywords: Finnish Log Construction, Market Study, Northeast China Market, Sustainable Building, Environmental Impact of Construction.

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Chapter 1 Introduction

Located in the heart of the northern forests, Finnish log houses have been an integral part of homes for generations and serve as a testament to the enduring relationship between human habitation and nature. These sturdy structures have withstood the harsh winters and bathed in the warm summer sun, with logs etched with life, work, and family stories. They stand as quiet witnesses to time, embodying a timeless link between the changing seasons and promoting a profound harmony with the environment.

As a teenager, I actively participated in building a log house and subsequently lived in one. This intensely personal experience shaped my view of log houses as more than just buildings. They are an integral part of the Finnish housing tradition and significant in Finland's cultural and residential landscape. Through my experience, I have come to appreciate these structures' beauty and the peace they offer.

During my professional journey in Finland's construction industry, I've worked as a project manager for several years. I've overseen various projects that involved reinforced concrete and timber structures. When I decided to pursue further education in China, my background naturally led me to explore the potential of log-based construction in the Chinese market. I'm heading on an exciting academic journey to introduce Finnish cultural heritage as a viable housing option in Northeast China.

1.1 The Purpose and Course of the Research

This study investigates the market opportunities for Finnish log construction in Northeast China, driven by a noticeable gap in existing research about this specific region. The main aim is to gain a deeper understanding of the timber construction market dynamics in Northeast China, focusing on evaluating the demand for and suitability of Finnish log structures within this market area. This study does not aim to provide absolute answers but lays a foundation for future studies and enhances understanding of timber construction practices in Northeast China.

Log buildings are constructed using various techniques and designs worldwide. This research explicitly studies Finnish log structures, which are unique to Finland in terms of their construction methods and designs. The study will not go into the technical, design, or construction details more than what is required. Instead, it will consider logging industry solutions as products and assess their suitability for the market.

Over the years, Finland's economy has been significantly reliant on the export of forest industry products like paper, pulp, and lumber [1]. Finland ranks as one of the most forest-rich countries globally, with forest coverage of 73.7% in 2020 [5]. This position and the growing international demand for low-emission construction solutions open up substantial global growth prospects for the Finnish log industry.

The study begins by addressing the critical issue of climate change and the global efforts to mitigate its effects. It explores the future ecological benefits of timber construction and how different timber construction methods could help reduce emissions in the worldwide construction industry. Additionally, the research provides an overview of timber construction in China. It takes a peek into the history of log construction in Northeast China, aiming to better understand the area under investigation.

Further, the brief history of log construction in Finland and its cultural significance are discussed. The study then outlines the various types of logs used in construction. It introduces the most common applications within the Finnish log industry, including detached homes, recreational buildings, and hybrid structures. These applications form the basis for the market overview and represent the scope of existing research.

The market overview aims to understand the current status of log construction in Northeast China and how it relates to the Finnish log industry. This involves assessing the market potential, the viewpoints of Finnish log industry companies on this market, customer interest and perceptions of log construction, and its overall suitability for construction projects considering the demands of the Chinese real estate sector. The collected information will be summarised as a SWOT analysis, incorporating additional aspects and thoughts on the market opportunities and challenges for the Finnish log industry in the target area.

In its concluding sections, this research synthesises its findings to evaluate the future potential of log construction and identify topics for additional investigation. The focus on Northeast China arises from pragmatic reasons, such as China's extensive geographical spread, making a comprehensive analysis of the Finnish log house market across the entire country unfeasible within the means of a single master's dissertation.

1.2 Research Methodologies

Considering the theoretical framework of the research area is still evolving, this study utilised a diverse array of data collection and analysis methods. Adopting a holistic research approach, it sourced information from various materials, including industry reports, articles, news pieces, interviews, and consumer surveys. The objective behind such varied methods was to ensure the information gathered was as comprehensive as possible.

To gather qualitative insights, company representatives were interviewed personally online. The interviews focused on their perceptions and experiences regarding the market potential for log houses in Northeast China. The aim was to capture in-depth insights that may not be available through conventional research or media channels.

Recognising the scarcity of existing research for a detailed market overview, the study expanded its data collection efforts through online surveys. These were directed at a broad audience of Northeast China residents to amass a significant volume of data. Analysing this data provided insights into consumer attitudes towards Finnish log industry products and the overall trend of timber construction in the region, now and in the future.

The greatest challenge in gathering information for the study was the language barrier, as the researcher's proficiency in Chinese was insufficient to engage with local studies or conduct interviews in Chinese. Consequently, this exploration primarily views the market potential from a Finnish perspective, which may limit the depth of insight into the Chinese viewpoint.

1.3 Emissions as a Catalyst for Change in Our World

Entering the 2020s, the tangible impacts of climate change are becoming increasingly evident globally. The 2023 Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) report highlights the rapid and widespread changes climate change has brought about in our atmosphere, oceans, cryosphere, and biosphere. These changes have significantly affected various weather and climate phenomena worldwide, leading to far-reaching and adverse effects on nature and humanity [36].

The effects of climate change are particularly pronounced in northern regions. Since 1979, the Arctic has been warming almost four times faster than the global average. This accelerated warming has resulted in rapid ice melt and significant ecosystem disruptions [34]. Similarly, low-lying areas, such as the Pacific Islands of Tuvalu and Kiribati, are grappling with severe challenges like freshwater scarcity, diminished local food production, and threats to coastal infrastructure

caused by rising sea levels [35].

Globally, climate change has intensified the frequency of floods, heavy rains, and storms. A notable example is the heavy rainfall in Central Europe in 2021, which led to devastating floods in Germany and Belgium, severely impacting infrastructure, lives, and economies [37]. Climate-induced drought also poses a significant global threat. In 2023, Somalia experienced its most severe drought in forty years, a crisis attributed to four consecutive failed rainy seasons that pushed millions to the brink of famine [38].

Human activities, especially carbon dioxide emissions, are significant contributors to the acceleration of climate change. The construction industry stands as the second-largest global producer of carbon dioxide, following the energy sector [33]. In 2021, the construction sector accounted for about 30% of global final energy consumption and was responsible for 27% of the energy sector's emissions, as indicated by the International Energy Agency (IEA) [29]. The Finnish government estimates that nearly half of the world's raw materials are used annually in construction [28].

In 2015, the construction industry was also noted for its significant consumption of the world's freshwater resources, utilising 25% of them, and for using large quantities of raw materials such as sand, wood, gravel, steel, cement, and plastic. This sector generates considerable solid waste and is characterised by high energy consumption levels and carbon dioxide emissions. Additionally, it contributes to the emission of nitrogen and sulphur compounds and delicate particulate matter [33].

In 2018, China was responsible for approximately 23% of the world's direct CO₂ emissions, 42% of indirect CO₂ emissions, and 41% of the total CO₂ emissions from global construction activities [44]. This significant contribution is partly due to China's construction industry's heavy reliance on steel and concrete, which are substantial emitters in the sector. This reliance is highlighted by the fact that in 2020, China alone accounted for half of the global cement production [45], with

most of this production being used domestically [101].

1.3.1 Global Climate Initiatives and Sustainable Development

The UN Environment Program's 2020 Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction underscores the urgent need to reduce energy consumption, transition to decarbonised energy production, and utilise sustainable materials in construction. The ultimate aim is to achieve a net-zero carbon building stock by 2050, with a nearer-term objective of reducing direct construction emissions by 50% and indirect emissions by 60% by 2030 [43].

Despite global efforts to combat climate change, including the landmark 2015 Paris Agreement, where 195 countries pledged to limit global warming to below 2 degrees Celsius [39], progress remains challenging. In 2023, the UN assessed that the world is off track to meet the Paris Agreement goals. The report emphasised that regions such as the UK and EU are not making sufficient changes to advance the agreement's objectives. This includes increasing clean energy production, phasing out all unabated fossil fuels, and combating deforestation [104].

Many international organisations and alliances have also established their standards for emissions reduction. Among these, the European Green Deal stands out as a transformative initiative that aims to combat climate change and drive sustainable development in Europe. Its main objective is to achieve climate neutrality for the EU by 2050, effectively reducing greenhouse gas emissions [40].

Countries highlighted in this research, such as Finland and China, have established ambitious carbon neutrality goals. Finland is working towards this goal by 2035 [41], while China aims to achieve it by 2060 [42]. In 2018, China introduced the "Ecological Civilization" program, focusing on green, sustainable development and integrating ecological health with economic and social progress [46].

The World Bank Group's 2022 Country Climate and Development Report for China outlines a comprehensive plan for achieving climate neutrality. The strategy includes boosting renewable energy, promoting electric vehicles and related infrastructure, supporting transitional communities, enhancing green building standards, reforming sustainable agriculture subsidies, and advocating for carbon offset initiatives. Additional proposals involve extending emissions trading, implementing low-carbon practices in state enterprises, and mandating climate-focused financial reporting [85].

From these initiatives, China has already begun actively pursuing sustainable development through diverse approaches, including significant investments in renewable energies like solar and wind power. The country is also endeavouring to reduce its reliance on fossil fuels by transforming coal-fired power plants to utilise alternative energy sources and prioritising recycling essential materials such as steel, aluminium, paper, and plastic [86].

China increasingly adopts prefabricated elements in its construction industry over traditional on-site casting. This shift offers multiple benefits, including reduced carbon footprint and increased efficiency. It significantly contributes to environmental sustainability and reinforces China's commitment to sustainable construction practices [86].

1.3.2 Wood Innovation for Tackle Emissions

In recent years, substantial global research has been conducted on the environmental benefits of timber construction, particularly emphasising its impact on reducing carbon dioxide emissions. The ecological advantages of wood construction are undeniable, offering a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to traditional building materials. Given the breadth and depth of research in this area, this research will focus on a few fundamental studies that specifically highlight the ecological benefits of timber construction.

Timber construction presents a potential solution to climate change, as wood is a renewable material with several advantages that reduce carbon dioxide emissions and support climate change mitigation. Sustainable wood use can help address challenges in energy and material usage [116]. A study examining the entire value chain of wood used in Switzerland demonstrates that wood use can bring significant environmental benefits and replace fossil-based materials in construction [118].

Pivotal studies by Hill et al. (2016) and Linkevičius et al. (2023) have also highlighted the positive environmental impact of wood construction and its role in sustainable development. These studies emphasise wood's role as a natural carbon sink, which continues to absorb carbon dioxide even after the construction phase, illustrating its ability to significantly reduce carbon dioxide emissions throughout its lifecycle compared to materials like concrete and steel [31] [32].

In 2022, Abed and colleagues extensively explored how mass timber meets structural requirements and exceeds conventional reinforced concrete in several aspects. The use of mass timber not only reduces emissions, energy use, and water consumption but also leverages its carbon sequestration properties to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, mass timber constructions demonstrate resilience against seismic activities, comply with fire safety standards, and enhance indoor air quality. This research supports mass timber as a sustainable construction alternative, considering life-cycle costs, durability, and health impacts [47].

In 2022, Avila et al. studied the environmental impact of timber versus reinforced concrete buildings using the Life Cycle Analysis methodology. Their findings indicate that utilising wood instead of reinforced concrete in the structural framework significantly reduces almost all environmental impacts for a 12-story building [117].

The benefits of log house construction have also been the focus of study, mainly drawing on Finnish research data. Seppo Romppainen, CEO of The Finnish Log House Industry Association, highlights the ecological benefits of log house construction. He points out that a medium-sized log

house for a living can sequester over 30 tons of carbon dioxide, equivalent to the emissions from a gasoline-powered car over 15 years [23].

Contrary to common misconceptions, wood has been found to possess excellent building properties. A study by Cabral and Blanchet (2021) reveals that wood buildings provide outstanding thermal insulation, leading to lower heating and cooling costs. The energy efficiency of timber construction and its impacts are essential to sustainable building [30] [119]. The acoustic properties of wood make it a suitable material for sound reflection and space soundproofing. Combining these thermal and acoustic benefits makes wood versatile and sustainable for various construction applications [12]. Notably, alongside these advantages, wood construction has also been acknowledged for its health benefits, particularly in improving indoor air quality, which further underscores its suitability for modern construction practices [9].

1.4 Promotion of Timber Construction on a Global Scale

Wood has been a predominant material in the construction of many homes, particularly in single-family residences, and is widely used in certain types of commercial buildings, especially low-rise structures across various global regions [45]. Cabral and Blanchet's 2021 report indicates that wood buildings comprise 90% of single-family homes in Canada and the United States, 45-70% in some European regions, and 45% in Japan [30]. Despite its already widespread use, many countries and communities are further promoting wood construction through various state and national programs.

Japan has taken a leading role in this initiative, actively advocating the use of wood through public regulations. A significant step was taken in 2010 when Japan enacted legislation mandating using wood materials in public buildings up to three stories. This law aims to foster self-sufficiency in wood production, encourage sustainable practices, and support wood product manufacturers through government loans and streamlined access to development permits [49].

In Finland, the government has supported timber construction since the 1990s, although the quantity of timber construction is not legally mandated, unlike in Japan. The latest initiative, launched in 2019, establishes clear goals for timber construction over four years, aiming to double the use of wood in construction and extend its application in the public sector [53].

By the 2020s, the European Union began championing wood construction across private and public sectors. The Build-in-Wood initiative, inaugurated in 2020, seeks to promote wood as a sustainable building material for multi-storey structures. It emphasises innovative solutions for materials, structures, and facades to bolster urban-rural connections. Its objectives are to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, establish a sustainable wood value chain, and enhance productivity in the construction industry [50].

France, a leading advocate of European timber construction, mandated that from 2022, at least 50% of public buildings should incorporate wood or other sustainable, biodegradable materials. This commitment is particularly evident in Paris, where the construction of natural materials such as wood, straw, and hemp are actively promoted. Notably, for the buildings constructed for the 2024 Paris Olympics, a requirement stipulates that all structures exceeding eight stories must be built entirely from timber, highlighting Paris's dedication to sustainable building practices [48].

In 2022, Australia launched a \$300 million Timber Building Program to foster mass timber construction and advance towards a net-zero emissions economy. Spearheaded by the Clean Energy Finance Corporation (CEFC), this program offers debt financing for eligible projects. It aims to lower construction-related emissions by adopting low-carbon engineered wood products [51].

Although China had not enacted specific legislation favouring wood construction as of early 2024, its growing interest in environmentally friendly building materials and methods aligns with its new environmental objectives. This emerging trend suggests that the popularity of wood construction is expected to increase, reflecting China's shift towards more sustainable building practices.

1.4.1 The State of Timber Construction in China

In architectural historiography, Liang Sicheng, a pioneering scholar in traditional Chinese architecture, provided a profound assessment of the evolutionary journey of Chinese wooden construction. After extensive research, he stated in 1946:

"The architecture of China can be aptly described as an inherently 'organic' entity. It emerged as an indigenous creation with its origins deeply rooted in the distant prehistoric past. This architectural form witnessed its formative phase during the Han dynasty, approximately at the dawn of the Christian era. Subsequently, it matured into a state of full splendour and vitality during the Tang dynasty, spanning the seventh and eighth centuries. The Song dynasty marked a refinement phase, as Chinese architecture acquired an aura of grace and elegance during the eleventh and twelfth centuries. However, with the advent of the Ming dynasty in the fifteenth century, it began to exhibit discernible signs of ageing, feebleness, and rigidity [54]."

Liang Sicheng's observations underscore the significant role of wood in the historical fabric of Chinese architecture. The evolution from predominantly earth and wood-based methods to those incorporating wood and bricks signifies a profound appreciation for wooden constructions and the mastery of carpentry, a defining feature of ancient Chinese architectural practices [56]. This exceptional craftsmanship is manifested in the enduring legacy of ancient pagodas, which have withstood the test of centuries due to their advanced building techniques [106].

While Sicheng's narrative references the history of timber construction in China, it can also be interpreted as an insightful commentary on the gradual displacement of wood in China's construction sector's fast-paced, urbanising landscape. In an era marked by the necessity for rapid construction of high-rise and large-scale structures, wood could not compete with the efficiency and durability offered by concrete and steel.

In urban landscapes across China, the prevalence of timber construction has been scarce, reflected in historical data on the extent of wood usage. According to a 2004 report, out of the annual construction of 10 million housing units in China, only about 500 were timber structures, often relying on imported materials and technology [55]. Furthermore, in 2009, it was reported that there were only about 2,000 wooden houses in major cities like Beijing and Shanghai [55].

Research history reveals increased timber construction studies in China in the early 2010s, which gradually continued towards the end of the decade. A 2012 study by Qu et al. evaluated China's wood-frame housing sector. Although identified as underdeveloped, the study acknowledged the sector's potential, particularly concerning energy-saving and low-carbon policies. The study emphasised the importance of knowledge dissemination and collaborative efforts to advance a more sustainable housing sector [55].

Entering the 2020s, the quantity of research has comfortably increased, and new studies have emerged. Examples include Jiawei Zhang et al.'s 2021 study, “Research on the Development of Wood Structure Buildings in China and Abroad,” which examines the development of timber-framed buildings. It analyses the characteristics, current status, and challenges such buildings face in China and on a global scale [71].

Signs of research on the ecological benefits of studying tall wood buildings appear to be an emerging trend in the Chinese research context. One such study, by Cindy X. Chen et al., titled “Comparative Life Cycle Assessment of Mass Timber and Concrete Residential Buildings: A Case Study in China,” undertook an in-depth life cycle assessment of tall buildings constructed using Cross-Laminated Timber (CLT), comparing their environmental impact to that of conventional reinforced concrete buildings [70].

In 2022, Zhang X. et al. studied the development of timber-concrete hybrid high-rise buildings in China. Their case studies include a 10-storey glulam timber frame with a concrete core business hotel in Guizhou province, designed for use as a luxury business hotel. The study provides details

of structural design and seismic performance, guiding subsequent timber-based hybrid high-rise structures and promoting the development of novel construction systems in China [110].

The actual volume of research on timber construction could be significantly larger. However, the researcher's limited proficiency in Chinese might prevent full access to potential research written in Chinese. Despite this challenge, timber construction research's volume and quality in the Chinese context show positive signs. If the growth in research continues, it is expected to signal a promising future for timber construction in China.

1.4.2 Recent Timber Projects in China

The number of timber construction projects in China has also risen recently. An exemplary instance of this trend is a significant office building project in Zhejiang Province that began in 2023 (Figure 1.1). This project features an innovative four-story mass timber structure. Focusing on sustainability, it integrates steel, concrete, and wood in a hybrid design. The building's concrete core strengthens the timber framework, enhancing its resistance to wind and seismic forces. The exterior, marked by diagonal glulam braces and thermal glass panels, creates a visually unique appearance [120].

Figure 1.1. Rendering of a four-story office building in Zhejiang. Canada Wood Group. (2023)

Constructed in 2021, The Tianfu Agriculture Exposition (Figure 1.2) in the greater metropolitan area of Chengdu showcases the growth in timber construction in China. Covering over 75,000m², its main hall is the largest timber structure in Asia and one of the largest globally. The structure comprises five interconnected vaults using innovative trusses that blend timber chords with steel webbing. These trusses facilitate spans of up to 110m and heights of 44m. Completed by an international team in just eighteen months, this project highlights Chengdu's agricultural economic strength and marks a significant feat in engineering and design [121].

Figure 1.2. The Tianfu Agricultural Expo Main Hall. StructureCraft. (2024).

In 2020, the Ministry of Housing and Urban-Rural Development of China spotlighted the advancement in wood construction by awarding the National Green Building Innovation Prize to two exemplary projects. The public decision in early 2021 emphasised these buildings' structural and ecological innovation. Leading the accolades was the main exhibition hall of the 10th Jiangsu Horticultural Exposition (Figure 1.3), which stood out for its primary use of scotch pine in

construction [122].

Figure 1.3. The main exhibition hall of the 10th Jiangsu Horticultural Exposition. School of Architecture, Southeast University. (2022).

The Haikou Citizen & Visitor Centre (Figure 1.4), located in Hainan province, was also recognised for its wood roof, featuring 350,000 pieces of western red cedar. This extensive use of wood made it one of Asia's most comprehensive roofs and earned it the second prize. This recognition reflects a broader trend towards innovative wood-frame construction, encouraging further advancements in this sustainable building practice [122].

Figure 1.4. Haikou Citizen & Visitor Centre. StructureCraft. (2024).

This conversation has been focused on a selection of contemporary timber construction efforts in China. As the country progresses towards sustainable and modern building practices, a more comprehensive range and several such initiatives are anticipated. The growing use of wood, especially in public sector projects, has been indicated as a positive direction for developing various timber construction techniques in China [122].

1.5 Wood Construction in North East China

Given that the primary objective of this dissertation is to explore the suitability of log construction in Northeast China, it is beneficial to briefly examine the history of wood and log building in the region. Such an investigation will shed light on the general familiarity and historical prevalence of log construction in the area, providing valuable insights into its potential acceptance in the present-day architectural landscape.

Other notable locations warrant consideration in the context of historical wooden structures in Northeastern China. One of the more renowned examples is found within Beiling Park in Shenyang. These wooden towers are quintessential representations of traditional Chinese architecture and form a fundamental component of the park's historical legacy. Critical structures, such as the Qing emperors' mausoleum, the watchtowers (Figure 1.5) along the walls, and other related buildings, predominantly feature wood.

Figure 1.5. Watchtower in Beiling Park. Taken by the author. (2023).

Harbin, located in Northeastern China, is known for its diverse architectural styles, including wooden buildings. A prominent example is the Lao Daowai Historic District, established collaboratively in the early 20th century by Russian immigrants and Chinese citizens. This district features well-preserved wooden structures representing a harmonious fusion of Russian and Chinese architectural elements, offering visitors a unique perspective on the area's cultural and architectural heritage [57].

Log cabin construction, with a history of over 3,000 years in Northeast China, is exemplified by the 'Mukeden' style, as depicted in Figure 1.6. This method involves stacking carefully carved logs, typically shaped into semi-cylinders, for constructing houses. The Mukeden style bears a striking resemblance to traditional forms of log construction found in Finland. Contrary to widespread assumptions, this style is not native to Chinese architectural traditions but draws influence from Eastern Russia. It gained prominence in regions such as Inner Mongolia, the forested areas of Northeast China, and the mountainous territories of Sichuan and Yunnan provinces [56].

Figure 1.6. Construction of Mukeden. Li & Jia. (2014).

Even today, some Mukeden structures built in the past are still visible. Jinjiang village, located at the base of the Changbai Mountains in Northeast China's Jilin province, is a remarkable enclave with a range of log houses dating back 300 years. Recognised as a critical provincial cultural relic, Jinjiang village is under protection for its historical significance. The construction techniques used in the Manchu timber houses of this region have been acknowledged as part of Jilin's intangible cultural heritage. Known as “the last wooden house village in the Changbai Mountains” and depicted in Figure 1.7, Jinjiang offers a vast array of the most extensively preserved ancient Manchu log house buildings in the area, representing a rich cultural and architectural legacy [58].

Figure 1.7. Well-preserved Manchu timber house in Jinjiang. GoJilin. (2022).

Log construction, an integral part of Northeast China's architectural legacy, has experienced a decline in its application within the modern construction landscape of China. This diminishing presence reflects not only evolving building techniques but also underscores a significant challenge — the incompatibility of traditional building methods with the current pace of population growth and housing demand. In their 2014 study, Li, W., and Jia, X. examined the decline of Mukeden structures in contemporary Chinese construction and identified three pivotal factors contributing to their diminishing prevalence.

Firstly, the demand for high-quality timber, essential for Mukeden construction, has become a formidable challenge. Deforestation and urban expansion have led to a severe depletion of this resource, particularly affecting those residing away from forested regions. This depletion highlights the negative environmental impact of current construction practices and raises critical questions regarding the sustainable management of natural resources. Secondly, their study points out a significant disparity in efficiency between natural materials, such as logs and moss, and their synthetic counterparts. This disparity underscores a pressing conflict between maintaining ecological integrity and pursuing efficiency in building materials [76].

There has been a noticeable change in the priorities of companies operating in the construction market. Due to the emphasis on profitability, structures in the Mukeden style are often seen as not financially viable, making them more of a niche market rather than a standard option in architecture. This situation is underscored by a growing preference for building high-rise structures, which offer better financial returns on land than log houses, marking a significant shift in construction trends [76].

Li, W., and Jia, X. emphasise that this trend reflects the economic landscape and underscores the urgent need to reassess the relevance and implementation of traditional construction techniques in today's rapidly changing context. Furthermore, researchers highlight the critical importance of cultural preservation at a time when economic considerations threaten to eclipse the richness of architectural heritage [76].

Chapter 2 Finnish Log Buildings

This section offers a concise history of Finnish log houses, describing the log types most commonly used and their traditional uses. Due to the market overview focus of this study, the technical details of log-based construction are not extensively examined. Furthermore, it highlights the three primary construction models prevalent in today's Finnish log industry: detached houses, recreational buildings, and hybrid structures. The aim is to provide insight into the products of the Finnish log industry and their application in modern construction practices. This overview seeks to lay the groundwork for future market overview aimed at exploring these building types within the context of Northeast China.

2.1 Finnish Log House History Briefly Explained

Log cabins originate from Scandinavia, Eastern Europe, and Northern Russia, with a history that dates back to the Bronze Age, around 3,500 BC [2]. These early structures were recorded by the Roman architect Vitruvius Pollio in his work "De Architectura," circa 30 BC [3]. In Finland, evidence of the first wooden constructions dates back to the late Stone Age, roughly 7,000 - 10,000 years ago [4]. The oldest surviving log structure in Finland, St. Henry's Preaching Cabin, located in Kokemäki, traces back to the 15th century [6].

Initially, log cabins were modest, built with horizontally stacked logs and vertical pillars for support. Their design exhibited early ingenuity in roofing materials such as birch bark and turf [7]. This design remained unchanged until the 11th century when smoke cabins emerged [8]. These cabins introduced smoke stoves or fireplaces but lacked chimneys, accumulating indoor smoke. The smoke was warm and vented through trapdoors or roof openings [10].

Significant advancements in log cabin design occurred in the 16th and 17th centuries, including the introduction of glass windows, improved roofing, and chimneys. These innovations improved living conditions while maintaining the traditional architectural style centred around a central fireplace [8]. The 19th century marked a new era for urban log houses in Finland, particularly among the bourgeoisie. Unlike traditional rustic styles, these urban log houses included contemporary features like kitchens and bedrooms [8]. The historical importance of this era is captured in the cities of Turku, Rauma, and Naantali. Rauma's Old Town (Figure 2.1), recognised as a UNESCO cultural heritage site since 1991, is a prime example of this architectural period [13].

Figure 2.1. Old Town of Rauma. Toivanen, J. (2020).

Post-World War II, Finnish housing saw a transformation. While timber and steel-concrete framed buildings became more prevalent, log construction remained popular for summer cottages and recreational housing [8] [11]. The 1970s was a pivotal era with the development of industrial methods for log manufacturing, leading to new perceptions and uses of log structures. By the 21st

century, log houses were viewed as traditional cottages and modern, eco-friendly residential options [52].

In recent years, there has been a revival in the popularity of log construction, especially in the detached house building sector. In 2021, approximately one in four new detached house projects in Finland utilised log structures [14]. Thanks to the development of new innovative building techniques, contemporary Finland now boasts a variety of highly modern log constructions for various uses, encompassing both private residences and public buildings.

2.2 Log as a Construction Material

Pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) is the primary wood material used in log construction, with spruce (*Picea abies*) also being utilised to some extent [17] [22]. Pine is preferred for its lightweight and softwood properties, which allow for efficient drying to an optimal moisture content of about 25% for processing, as illustrated in Figure 2.2. Its texture makes it suitable for glueing, and the heartwood's high decay resistance makes pine particularly well-suited for outdoor use [24]. With pine forests accounting for 44% of Finland's forest area, there's a steady and reliable supply of this timber for construction [25].

Figure 2.2. Pine on the left and spruce on the right. Puuproffa. (2023).

Spruce, making up about 36% of Finland's forest stock, ranks as the country's second most prevalent tree species. Characterised by its lightweight, softness, and uniform texture, spruce is highly workable and well-suited for tasks like lathe turning. It also has favourable adhesive properties and responds well to surface treatments. However, its lower resistance to severe weather and its susceptibility to fungal decay and insect attacks somewhat limit its use in log construction [26] [27]. Spruce's propensity to warp and form larger cracks than pine further restricts its application in log-based building projects [22].

2.2.1 Log Types

In log construction, the selection of log type is influenced by the building's design and intended function. The primary varieties are round, massive, and laminated logs with distinct features and uses.

Round logs retain the tree trunk's original form (Figure 2.3), preserving their authentic shape and essence. The traditional process for round log construction involves carefully removing the bark to reveal the wood beneath. This highlights the timber's natural beauty and readies it for further treatment. Round logs are generally lightly sanded to ensure a smooth surface, though variations in thickness are natural due to each log's unique characteristics [16]. These logs can be shaped either by machine for uniformity or by hand for a more artisanal touch, offering flexibility in their production [15]. While not commonly used in modern residential buildings in Finland, round logs remain a favourite for vacation properties, especially in tranquil lakeside or forest environments.

Deadwood, or weathered pine, is ancient pine wood that has slowly decomposed in wetlands [16]. Over time, this wood transforms, becoming highly durable and visually appealing. Historically, it was primarily used as firewood, but its unique appearance has recently made it a sought-after material in construction [17]. Deadwood has a significant ecological role as it is an essential habitat for many animal species, playing a crucial role in biodiversity conservation. This environmental importance and scarcity in Finland have significantly increased its value [19].

Figure 2.3. Round log and deadwood log. Puuproffa. (2023).

Massive log represents a shift from traditional log construction to industrialisation. In this method, logs are manufactured industrially from a single piece of wood through processes like sawing, planing, or turning. These industrially produced logs are exact copies of one another, streamlining and simplifying the on-site construction process of a log house. Industrialisation aims to lower costs and accelerate the production process of log construction [22].

As illustrated in Figure 2.4, laminated logs are constructed by adhering parallel lamellas together using a robust adhesive. This construction technique allows for producing logs with greater cross-sectional dimensions, improving their stability. The bonding process facilitates meticulous quality control, resulting in consistently high-quality structures. Laminated logs are more resistant to moisture-induced deformations, such as warping and cracking, than solid wood logs [15].

Figure 2.4. Massive log and laminated log. Puuproffa. (2023).

Laminated logs are prized for their flexibility, which facilitates the creation of diverse architectural styles. They can be tailored in shape and size, providing buildings with a modern and unique aesthetic. This adaptability grants architects and builders a wide range of creative options. With these advantages, it's clear why laminated logs have overtaken solid logs as the preferred material in the Finnish timber industry [21].

An additional advantage of laminated logs is their ability to minimise the natural settling or deformation that affects wood and timber structures over time. This issue can be effectively addressed by integrating vertical timber lamellae into the structure of timber beams. Nowadays, many manufacturers of timber-framed houses offer their own industrially manufactured, non-settling laminated timber beams, enabling the construction of taller and more complex wooden structures [78].

2.3 Applications of Logs in Construction

In Finland, the tradition of timber construction is mainly celebrated in creating leisure homes like cabins, which remain a favoured choice for holiday spots and recreational zones. The magnificent log cabins found in the ski resorts of Finnish Lapland exemplify this trend. Timber logs in modern construction have expanded their use, moving beyond conventional single-family homes to encompass a broader range of applications.

Over recent years, the scope of timber construction has widened to include public projects, such as schools and daycare centres, showcasing the adaptability of logs to various building types. Finnish firms specialising in log house construction have led this advancement, pioneering new techniques for building taller log structures. These innovations often involve combining logs with other materials, such as steel or reinforced concrete, to fulfil the requirements of modern architecture.

This section will highlight the most prevalent types of log construction, aiming to clearly and succinctly describe these varieties. The emphasis will be on outlining their fundamental characteristics and applications to offer a well-rounded understanding of the Finnish log industry's vast structures, particularly considering the potential for exports to markets like China.

2.3.1. Detached Houses

In the current construction landscape, each log house company presents its unique array of timber homes, with single-family residences being particularly prominent. These homes come in various designs and sizes to meet diverse personal and family requirements. Laminated timber logs are frequently chosen for such homes due to their suitability for constructing single-family homes.

Massive log construction is another choice for single-family homes. However, a significant challenge in this method lies in balancing structural integrity with the need for adequate log

thickness and thermal insulation. This balancing act is crucial for laminated and solid log constructions, ensuring that single-family residences achieve structural stability and energy efficiency [83]. A typical example in Finland is the single-story log house, as shown in Figure 2.5. These houses can be seen nationwide, from rural settings to urban neighbourhoods like Helsinki, Espoo, and Tampere.

Figure 2.5. A log house made from laminated timber logs. Aatela, I. (2023).

Log houses have surged in popularity as primary residences, a trend credited to their blend of traditional charm with modern technological advancements. These homes have contemporary features, including well-equipped kitchens, spacious bathrooms, and versatile living spaces. They are often integrated with advanced heating, air conditioning, and intelligent control systems, enhancing their functionality in modern living.

Modern log houses are increasingly designed as two-story structures to meet the demands of those requiring more space. These multi-story homes utilise construction methods similar to those of their single-story counterparts. While not as common as single-story homes, two-story single-

family log houses remain essential to the Finnish residential landscape. These homes demonstrate the versatility and adaptability of log construction and are widely present throughout Finland, as shown in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6. Two-story log house. Kontiotuote Oy. (2023).

Finnish log houses have made their mark in China, with standout instances like the one in Hangzhou depicted in Figure 2.7. Constructed by the Finnish company Honka, this house merges Finnish and Chinese architectural elements. It is designed to suit Hangzhou's climate, which is known for its heavy rainfall and humidity. To combat these environmental challenges, the structure features an elevated base. Additionally, the ground floor is made of concrete, a decision influenced by the area's insect population and the need for enduring strength in a damp environment [72].

Figure 2.7. Finnish log house in Hangzhou, China. Honkarakenne Oyj. (2021).

The spatial requirements of detached houses pose challenges in urban areas with high population density. These houses, designed predominantly for single-family living, frequently encounter limitations on vertical expansion due to the structural constraints inherent in log construction. Consequently, they may not be optimal for areas that accommodate larger populations within constrained land spaces. In contrast, detached log houses are more appropriate for settings with lower population density, such as rural areas or locations farther from urban centres, where the pressure on space is considerably reduced.

2.3.2. Recreational Buildings

In Finland, using logs in holiday cottages is a unique aspect of the country's construction traditions. These cottages, typically situated along scenic lakeshores and within lush forests, cater to diverse personal preferences through various log types. The Finnish log house market has recently expanded to include modern designs that accommodate year-round living. This development represents a shift towards providing log houses that serve as vacation retreats and fulfil the requirements of permanent residences, as illustrated in Figure 2.8.

Figure 2.8. Modern recreational building made from logs. Kontiotuote Oy. (2023).

The region of Lapland in Northern Finland is renowned for its extensive array of traditional round-log (Figure 2.9) and deadwood-log buildings. Characterised by their distinctive features, these structures are particularly favoured for constructing hotels, resort accommodations, and restaurants. Their popularity is most noticeable in Northern Finland's tourism-focused areas, with ski resorts prominently featuring these traditional log buildings as prime illustrations of their application.

Figure 2.9. Traditional round log building. Kuortaneen Hirsitalot Oy. (2019).

Over recent decades, Finnish firms have significantly exported holiday resorts and leisure log structures to China. In 2017, the Finnish company Honka delivered a Welcome Center and a café-restaurant at the Haitou Valley site, depicted in Figure 2.10. This site is strategically positioned north of Beijing, close to where the alpine events of the 2022 Winter Olympics were hosted. The design of the Welcome Center and its associated facilities aimed to cater to the leisure needs of discerning clients, with a particular focus on family-oriented services and a dedication to offering high-quality amenities [84].

Figure 2.10. Welcome Center in Haitou Valley. Honkarakenne. (2019).

Holiday cottages in Finland are often found in secluded areas, providing serene escapes from the bustle of urban life. These settings allow for a deep connection with nature, promoting relaxation and various outdoor activities. Particularly in winter, these cottages become popular destinations, offering luxury experiences such as skiing and the chance to witness unique experiences, like the Northern Lights. While integral to Finnish cultural heritage, the concept of holiday cottages may vary in significance and functionality in different cultural contexts. In areas where the tradition of holiday cottages is not established or practical, these retreats may not hold the same cultural importance or utility.

2.3.3. Hybrid Buildings

Logs often require support from other materials for more complex and taller construction projects. Recent technological advancements have made it easier to incorporate logs into hybrid structures, combining them with concrete and steel. This approach facilitates the construction of larger structures, such as apartment complexes and other significant construction endeavours [59].

The application of log construction in public projects has significantly increased in recent years. The Monio project in Tuusula, completed in 2023, is a prime example. This multifaceted building accommodates a high school, community college, arts education facilities, and the Tuusula Institute, demonstrating the versatility of log construction in multifunctional environments (Figure 2.11). Another notable instance is the log school in Pudasjärvi, inaugurated in 2016. Serving 800 students, it combines academic and sports facilities, illustrating the practicality and appeal of log structures in educational settings [60]. Additionally, establishing Finland's largest log-built daycare centre in Kemi in 2021 further exemplifies the adaptability of log construction across various educational formats [87].

Figure 2.11. Monio in the municipality of Tuusula. Puuinfo. (2023).

The increasing presence of multi-story apartment buildings featuring log-based hybrid construction in Finland reflects a significant shift in construction trends fueled by advancements in log-building techniques within the Finnish timber industry. In contrast to those built solely with reinforced concrete, the comparatively higher investment required for these log-based apartment buildings is a notable factor influencing this emerging trend.

Prominent examples of log house construction are found in various areas, including Pudasjärvi [59] and Inkoo, along Finland's southern coast. These areas are distinguished by their innovative approach to wood construction. Figure 2.12 showcases the completion of the first two three-story log apartment buildings in 2022 situated in this region. These structures represent a vital component of a larger regional development initiative that focuses on using wood in construction processes [124].

Figure 2.12. Log apartment buildings in Inkoo. Honkatalot. (2022).

Taller log buildings can be incorporated into the cores of holiday resorts. An example is in Lapland, adjacent to the Pyhä ski resort, where two hybrid log holiday apartment complexes are being developed (Figure 2.13). The first of these hotel buildings was inaugurated in February 2023, while the second is still under development [124].

Figure 2.13: Hybrid log holiday apartment complexes in Pyhä ski resort. Honkatalot. (2023).

The development of log-based multi-story apartment buildings is currently experiencing an upward trend, primarily driven by the innovative approaches of Finnish leading log house companies. They have taken a step further by openly sharing their structural and design concepts tailored for high-rise log buildings. This act offers essential technical insights to designers, architects, and professionals in the industry. This collaborative spirit is pivotal in exploring and enhancing the possibilities of log-based hybrid buildings in the future [123].

Chapter 3 Market Overview

This section delves into the log house market in Northeast China, analysing demographic data from three provinces to assess the current market dynamics and the interest in the Finnish log industry. It also discusses a survey of 400 Chinese respondents to gauge their perceptions of Finnish log houses and the market's potential in the region. Furthermore, it considers brand image, market trends, target markets, and customer segmentation. Concluding with a SWOT analysis, this section encapsulates the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats facing the log house market in Northeast China, offering a comprehensive overview of its prospects and challenges.

3.1 Market Area Demographics

Historically referred to as Manchuria (Figure 3.1), Northeast China includes the modern provinces of Liaoning, Jilin, and Heilongjiang. In some contexts, it may also encompass a portion of the Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region. In the context of this study, parts of Inner Mongolia are not considered within the scope of the study. Geographically, Northeast China is defined by natural borders. To the north, it is separated from the Russian Far East by the Amur, Argun, and Ussuri Rivers. To the south, it is delineated by the Yalu and Tumen Rivers, which mark its division from Korea. Additionally, the region shares its western boundary with Inner Mongolia and Hebei provinces [61].

Figure 3.1. Map of North East China. (Yang & Pettit, 2018).

3.1.1 Liaoning Province

Liaoning Province is a significant region in northeastern China, occupying approximately 145,900 square kilometres. As of the 2022 census, it boasts a population of around 41.97 million [64]. In 2023, Liaoning's residents' median age was 39 years [66]. Geographically, Liaoning is the southernmost province in this part of China. It is notably adjacent to North Korea, with the Yalu River forming a natural boundary between the two [63]. The province is distinguished by the presence of two principal cities: Shenyang, its capital, and Dalian, strategically located along the southern coast (Figure 3.2) [62].

Figure 3.2. Map of Liaoning Province. (Yang & Pettit, 2018).

Liaoning Province is divided into 14 prefectures, encompassing a diverse administrative structure that includes 59 urban districts, 25 counties, and 16 county-level cities, such as Anshan, Liaoyang, and Dandong. Ethnic minorities, comprising just over 15 per cent of the population, are a significant aspect of Liaoning's demographic fabric, with the Manchu, Mongol, Hui, and Korean communities being particularly noteworthy [62].

The geographical landscape of Liaoning is characterised by its diversity, with elevated regions in the west and east, contrasted by the flatter terrain of the central area and the southern peninsula. The expansive Northeast Plain dominates the central region, while the eastern border features the Changbai Mountains. The Liaodong Peninsula, nestled between the Bo Sea and the Yellow Sea, boasts a unique coastal environment marked by a series of islands. The province's topography is broadly categorised into four zones: the central plains, the Liaodong Peninsula, the western highlands, and the eastern mountain zone [62] [64].

From an economic perspective, Liaoning is a powerhouse in Northeastern China and is recognised as one of the country's critical industrial provinces. Its economic stature is attributed mainly to significant investments, including state-funded projects since 1949 [64]. Liaoning's financial framework is firmly rooted in traditional secondary industries such as mining. The proportion of these industries in the provincial GDP has fluctuated slightly: 50% in 1992, 48% in 1999, 50% in 2007, and 46% in 2015. Within this sector, heavy industry is particularly dominant, contributing over 70% to the total output of secondary industries and playing a crucial role in the overall GDP of the province [65].

3.1.2 Jilin Province

Jilin Province's approximately 187,000 square kilometres expanse is a central area in northeastern China [62]. The province's permanent resident count reached 23.48 million in 2022 [67]. In 2023, Jilin's population had a median age of 39 [68]. The administrative structure of Jilin encompasses nine prefectures, which are segmented into 21 urban districts, 20 county-level cities, and 19 counties. Notably, the provincial capital, Changchun, is positioned on the fringe of the local plain, surrounded by the Dahei Mountains, which marks a significant geographical feature of the region (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3. Map of Jilin Province. (Yang & Pettit, 2018).

Jilin Province's geography is diverse, comprising three central regions: the eastern mountainous area, the western plains, and a central zone of rolling hills. The terrain gradually descends from the highlands in the southeast to the Northeast Plain in the northwest. In the eastern part of Jilin, the mountain ranges form parallel chains interspersed with broad valleys. Among these, the Changbai Mountains near the Korean border are particularly notable. This range exhibits volcanic activity and includes Mount Baitou (also known as Mount Paektu in Korean), the highest peak in both northeastern China and North Korea, located along the border [69].

Ethnically, Jilin's population is diverse, with ethnic minorities making up nearly 8 per cent of its total population. The province is especially significant for hosting over half of China's Korean

population. The western region of Jilin, part of the Northeast China Plain, is the province's agricultural hub [62]. Jilin specialises in food crops like rice, maize, grain sorghum, millet, and beans. The Yianbian Korean Autonomous Prefecture in eastern Jilin is known for its rice production, playing a significant role in northern China's rice sector. The province also produces commercial crops such as sugar beets, tobacco, flax, sunflower, and sesame [69].

Timber harvesting is crucial in the upper Sungari River basin, supporting construction and milling. In the east, the forestry industry focuses on pulp and paper production. Jilin's industrial sector is relatively developed, with key industries including automobile manufacturing, chemicals, machine tools, power generation, and forest-related products. Industrial activities are primarily concentrated in Changchun and Jilin, the province's two largest cities [69].

3.1.3 Heilongjiang Province

Heilongjiang Province (Figure 3.4), China's northernmost region, is named after the Heilong Jiang, known internationally as the Black Dragon River or the Amur River. This province shares its international border with Russia, delineated by the Heilong and Ussuri rivers. Covering a significant area of about 454,000 square kilometres, Heilongjiang's population was approximately 30.99 million as of 2022 [62] [73]. In 2023, the average age of residents in Heilongjiang was recorded as 39 years [74].

Figure 3.4. Map of Heilongjiang Province. (Yang & Pettit, 2018).

Heilongjiang Province is administratively divided into 13 prefectures, which encompass 65 urban districts, 19 county-level cities, and 44 counties. Ethnic minorities, constituting approximately 3.5 per cent of the total population, include indigenous groups like the Daur, Xibe, Oroqen, and Hezhe. The population distribution in Heilongjiang is uneven, with a higher density in the southern part, particularly around the provincial capital, Harbin, and other key cities such as Daqing and Mudanjiang [62].

Geographically situated in northeastern China, Heilongjiang occupies about half of the extensive Northeast Plain and is bordered by mountain ranges on three sides. The province's terrain is

predominantly lowland, with elevations exceeding 1000 meters only in the southeastern and northwestern mountainous regions and specific peaks within the Xiao Hinggan Range [75].

Initially, much of the plain areas in Heilongjiang were covered by forest prairie, which has been significantly reduced due to cultivation, leaving primarily poplars. The region is rich in herbaceous plants, pasture grasses, and sorghums. The central plain was once prairie-steppe, with the western part being drier. In contrast, the mountainous areas are densely forested with conifers and a mix of conifer and broad-leaved species, including red and white pines, Manchurian ash, cork trees, and catalpas. These forests are also home to numerous economically valuable wild plants and mushrooms [75].

As a significant producer of raw timber in China, Heilongjiang's primary sources are the Da and Xiao Hinggan ranges. The province also plays a crucial role in manufacturing, with a diverse production range that includes motor vehicles, generators, agricultural machinery, locomotives, building materials, flax fabrics, beet sugar, dairy products, and beverages. The industrial sector in Heilongjiang primarily capitalises on its rich mineral resources, exemplified by using locally produced petroleum in the petrochemical industry [75].

3.2 Log Construction Companies in China

A scarcity of reliable written sources hinders the evaluation of the log construction industry in Northeast China. Given the region's geographical location, it is probable that more detailed information about companies in the global market might be available in languages such as Chinese or Russian.

Given the limited data, exploring the log market in the broader context of China while focusing on activities in Northeast China appears to be a more practical approach. Despite the challenges posed by language barriers, an initial assessment can be conducted on countries known for their expertise in log house construction. The most prominent among these countries include Finland, Russia,

Canada, and Japan.

Signs indicate that Russian log house suppliers have identified China as an essential market. One example is a company called KLM Art, which established an office in Linyan, Changdong Province, in 2014 and has since been active in delivering log buildings to various locations in China, including areas near Shanghai and Beijing [90].

The involvement of Canadian companies in this sector is significant, exemplified by Cabintek, which specialises in exporting Canadian log houses to China [91]. Similarly, BESS, a Japanese log construction firm, has successfully established its presence within the Chinese log building market [89]. While online searches reveal Chinese companies' engagement in the log-building business, accurately assessing the market situation remains challenging due to the scarcity of comprehensive information.

In examining the Finnish log house exports to Northeast China, the case of Rovaniemen Hirsitalot Oy is particularly notable. According to a news article 2015, this Finnish company supplied 25 log houses to the Northeast China region [92]. However, it appears that the company's activities in this market have ceased in the subsequent years. By 2020, Rovaniemen Hirsitalot Oy was registered inactive in the business registry, with the latest financial information dating back to 2018 [93].

Among Finnish companies, Honkarakenne Oyj (or Honka) has been the most visible player in the Chinese market. The company's official website documents several projects and business deals in China, although most reports are from before the COVID-19 pandemic. In recent years, information has been sparse, with Honkarakenne acknowledging in 2021 that the pandemic significantly affected their exports to China [88].

An examination of Honka's revenue composition offers insights into the scale of its foreign trade. In 2022, the company reported a revenue of 75 million euros [80]. A significant portion of the

company's net sales, approximately 70%, was generated within Finland, while exports comprised over one-third of their total net sales. Currently, the company's export efforts are primarily focused on Central Europe, the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), and various regions in Asia [79] [81].

3.2.1 Insight from Kontio

Given the limited access to insights on the market from publications, a strategic decision was made to seek information on the Finnish log industry regarding the Chinese market through interviews. Email invitations for interviews were extended to the six most known Finnish log house manufacturers. Among these, Kontio (formally known as Kontiotuote Oy) was the sole company that agreed to participate in an interview expressly for this research study.

Kontio is the global leader in log building manufacturing, which is highlighted by its thorough oversight of the production process, from acquiring raw materials to completing construction. Reporting a turnover of 95.3 million euros for the fiscal year 2022, it is the world's largest producer in the logging industry by revenue. With a presence in over 20 countries, Kontio showcases a significant international scope, which augments its impact on the domestic market. As of the end of 2022, it boasted a workforce of 284 dedicated employees [77].

The interview with Kontiotuote Oy was conducted via Microsoft Teams in April 2023, featuring Hanna Haipus, the B2B Business Director, and Mikko Löf, the Planning Manager, as interviewees. This thematic interview was designed to facilitate an open dialogue rather than adhere to a predefined set of questions, allowing for an in-depth exploration of the situation, opportunities, and challenges within the Chinese market.

Currently, Kontio's marketing efforts are primarily directed towards the European, Japanese, and Canadian markets, with France and Sweden emerging as a particularly significant export destination in recent years. Additionally, there has been an increase in interest in log construction

from Middle Eastern countries, signalling a broadening of Kontio's market reach [94].

Kontio's involvement in the Chinese market has declined significantly from its more prominent position over a decade ago. Despite this reduced presence, Kontio recognises China's considerable potential as a future export destination, given its vast population and substantial purchasing power. Kontio is keen to revitalise its business operations in China, aiming to capitalise on the market's significant opportunities [94].

Kontio faces challenges in understanding the current dynamics and establishing a presence in the Chinese market, primarily due to its relatively small size compared to the vast Chinese market. Hanna Haipus, the B2B Business Director, articulates this challenge by stating, "Being a relatively small operator in the global construction arena, our solo efforts to penetrate the Chinese market encounter numerous hurdles." She advocates for a collective approach, suggesting that Finnish log house companies could significantly enhance their prospects in China by acting together. Specifically, creating a cluster of Finnish companies could be an effective strategy to enter the Chinese market [94].

There are clear signs of the Finnish log industry's intention to target the Chinese market collectively. Finnish log industry companies have united to form an entity known as The Finnish Log House Industry Association. This association's primary aim is to cultivate and globally promote the exports of log industry products. Currently, the association has approximately 20 member companies among its ranks. One of its key goals is developing the Chinese market segment across various dimensions in partnership with Chinese counterparts [82] [94].

The Finnish Log House Industry Association is collaborating with Chinese construction authorities to develop a unified standard for log construction. This initiative seeks to streamline regulations, guidelines, and construction techniques, all of which are tailored to accommodate the specific needs and preferences of the Chinese market. These guidelines aim to provide a detailed framework that outlines the essential principles and practices of log construction, intentionally

crafted to be compatible with Chinese construction methodologies [94].

The Finnish log house industry is not alone in this effort to establish standardised log construction practices alongside Chinese collaborators. This initiative also includes active participation from countries such as Canada, Japan, and Russia, all working diligently with Chinese partners to develop their log construction codes. This concerted international action highlights the fierce global competition to access the Chinese market, suggesting an even more intense contest for market share ahead. Mikko Löf succinctly captures this competitive spirit by stating, "Every country wants their share of the Chinese market" [94], reflecting the widespread ambition to secure a foothold in this promising market.

The interview emphasises that, despite the ongoing efforts towards collaborative development, there is a need to consider promoting growth in the log construction sector within Finland and on a global scale. The current global construction landscape, predominantly favouring steel and concrete, exhibits a notable deficiency in specialised education for log construction. Löf suggests that more investment is needed globally in log construction's education and planning stages [94].

In pursuit of more profound insights into the Chinese market, representatives from Kontio highlighted several critical questions aimed at improving their operational effectiveness in China. These questions are centred around understanding the market dynamics and consumer perceptions in China, as follows:

1. What is the general attitude of the Chinese population towards timber products?
2. What preconceptions might the Chinese hold about Finnish timber construction?
3. Is there an openness among the Chinese populace to invest in eco-friendly construction methods?
4. To what extent do ecological goals influence construction priorities among the Chinese?
5. What are the current trends in wood construction within China?

6. What are the primary quality concerns of the Chinese regarding timber products, and how receptive are they to foreign timber construction solutions?
7. What level of testing, certification, and compliance with product-related requirements is expected by the Chinese market?

These inquiries mark the initial stage of exploring the Chinese market, emphasising the need to gather fundamental insights. It's important to note that this information is derived from an interview with just one Finnish log construction company. However, given Kontio's status as a leading figure in the global log-building industry, the insights obtained provide a valuable perspective. Thus, these questions lay a foundation for informed speculations regarding the trends and conditions of the Finnish log industry in China.

3.3 Web Survey for Consumer Attitudes

This market research aimed to assess attitudes and awareness regarding Finnish timber construction among residents of Northeast China through quantitative data collection methods. A web survey was developed, composed of 12 questions designed for simple 'yes/no' responses, though participants could skip questions. The questions included:

1. Which age group do you belong to?
2. Which province do you live in?
3. Have you heard of Finnish wooden houses?
4. Do you find the log house in the picture suitable for living in?
5. Do you find the log-based apartment building in the picture attractive?
6. would you be willing to purchase or live in a wooden house in China if the pricing were similar to other housing options?
7. Would you be willing to live in a log-based apartment building in China?
8. Do you think log houses are a safe housing option?

9. Do you think log houses are a healthy housing option?
10. If log houses significantly reduce carbon dioxide emissions associated with construction and living, would you consider them a housing option?
11. Do you think log houses' construction and living costs are higher than other housing types?
12. Do you think there will be an increase in wooden constructions in your area in the future?

The survey's objective extended beyond gauging the awareness of Finnish log construction; it also aimed to understand the general attitude towards timber construction in the area and perceptions regarding its safety, health benefits, affordability, and environmental impact.

3.3.1 Participant Demographics, Sample Size, and Margin of Error

The survey began with two initial questions to identify the respondents' age groups and provinces of residence in China. The decision to omit gender as a question was strategic, intended to simplify the survey process, and made under the assumption that gender was not considered crucial for this survey. The online nature of the survey necessitated specifying the respondents' provinces to guarantee that the feedback accurately reflected the targeted research area.

Of the 562 responses received, 120 were from provinces outside Northeast China and were subsequently excluded from the study. Additionally, responses from 34 individuals in the Inner Mongolia region were not considered. Another eight respondents did not specify their province of residence and were excluded from the analysis. Consequently, the study focused on 400 responses from the Northeast China region, distributed as 175 from Liaoning province, 134 from Heilongjiang, and 91 from Jilin province, as depicted in Chart 3.5.

Chart 3.5. “Which province do you live in?”

Among the respondents from Northeast China, 397 provided their age group, while three opted not to. The age distribution was as follows: 101 respondents were 18 to 24 years, 183 were between 25 and 34 years, 97 were within the 35 to 44 age bracket, ten respondents were 45 years or older, and six were under 18 years. Chart 3.6 reveals that 96% of the participants fell into the 18 to 44 age groups, showcasing an optimal age distribution for this survey. This demographic predominantly consists of relatively young individuals considering buying or investing in homes or will be in the market.

Chart 3.6. “Which age group do you belong to?”

For the validity of the survey research, it's crucial to assess the study's margin of error (MOE). When evaluating the MOE, the responses of 400 participants were considered to concern the entire population of Northeast China. The MOE is calculated using the following formula:

$$MOE = Z \frac{\sqrt{p(1-p)}}{n}$$

In this formula, Z is a value that corresponds to the chosen confidence level, indicating the degree of confidence in the results. For a commonly used 95% confidence level, a Z -score of 1.96 is selected. The variable p represents the proportion of positive responses in the sample, and in cases where this proportion is unknown, a value of 0.5 is conventionally assumed [95]. n denotes the sample size, which, in this instance, is 400. By inserting these values into the formula, the MOE is calculated as:

$$MOE = (1.96) \frac{\sqrt{0.5(1-0.5)}}{400} \approx 0.049$$

This calculation results in a margin of error of roughly 5%. This means that, at a 95% confidence level, the survey responses could differ by about 5% from the results presented. However, a more extensive survey than the one conducted for this study would be required to achieve absolute certainty and precision. Utilising larger sample sizes and incorporating more detailed questions would help reduce the margin of error and yield more precise results.

3.3.2 Brand Image

One of the study's key focal points was to evaluate the recognition and brand perception of Finnish log houses among residents of Northeast China. The objectives of this research extended beyond simply measuring awareness. It also aimed to explore perceptions related to the suitability, safety, and health benefits of these houses as living spaces—additionally, the survey aimed to gauge the participants' interest in purchasing or living in log-based homes.

The survey began with questions designed to assess the participants' general awareness of Finnish log houses. Of those who responded, 323 individuals reported being familiar with Finnish log houses, 62 respondents were unaware, and 15 chose not to answer, as illustrated in Chart 3.7.

The survey revealed that over 80% of the participants were acquainted with the concept of Finnish log houses, demonstrating notable potential for introducing Finnish log construction techniques to Northeast China. Nevertheless, about 20% of respondents did not recognise the concept or chose not to answer. This recognition level provides a solid base for crafting marketing strategies to bolster the Finnish log house footprint in the area.

Chart 3.7. “Have you heard of Finnish log houses?”

After the initial questions, the survey presented participants with two conceptual images of log buildings to gain further insight into their views. The first image showed a 1.5-story detached log house, while the second depicted a four-story hybrid log apartment building, as seen in Figure 3.8. Respondents were then asked to assess the attractiveness of these structures as potential living spaces. The goal was to gather fundamental insights into the common perceptions of Finnish log buildings and their design aesthetics.

Figure 3.8. Concept images of log structures used in the survey. Kontio. (2023).

Chart 3.9 indicates that, regarding the 1.5-story detached house, 368 respondents considered it an appealing living option, whereas only 19 expressed an opposing view, and 24 abstained from responding. Likewise, 356 participants had a positive impression of the four-story apartment building, 33 had an unfavourable opinion, and 11 chose not to respond. In both instances, more than 90% of the feedback was positive, indicating that the buildings featured in the survey's conceptual images are perceived very favourably regarding their aesthetic appeal and brand image within the log construction industry.

Chart 3.9. "Do you find the log houses in the pictures attractive for living in?"

Specific questions were posed to participants to explore perceptions related to the brand and safety of log-based construction. They were asked about their views on the safety of log houses and whether they considered them healthy living environments. Concerning safety, 312 participants viewed log houses as secure, 78 did not, and ten opted not to respond. In healthiness, 359 respondents believed that log houses offer a healthy living environment, 30 disagreed, and 11 did not respond to the question, as outlined in Chart 3.10.

Chart 3.10. “Do you see log houses as safe and healthy housing options?”

Log houses were perceived as significantly beneficial for health, yet there was a noticeable increase in 'no' responses concerning safety compared to other survey sections. This concern about the safety of log houses might stem from worries about fire safety in wooden structures. Since the survey format did not allow for expressing more detailed opinions, understanding the safety concerns can be further explored through studies on similar topics.

In 2016, Qinian Hu and colleagues conducted a study that examined Chinese consumers' attitudes towards timber-framed houses. Their research highlighted fire safety as a significant concern for the residential safety of wood-based buildings among Chinese respondents. Of 587 survey participants, only 28% viewed wood as fire-resistant and slightly less than 40% perceived it as somewhat safe. In contrast, 30% considered wood construction a direct fire hazard [96].

The stigma around fire safety in wooden construction poses a significant challenge for Kontio in the international market. Despite modern log industry products meeting fire safety standards equivalent to those of reinforced concrete buildings, overcoming this misconception is complicated. This is mainly due to existing prejudices and insufficient awareness of contemporary developments in wood-based construction [94].

3.3.3 Market Trend

The survey aimed to evaluate Chinese individuals' interest in purchasing log-based buildings and explore how eco-friendly and low-emission options could influence their decision to buy such homes. Participants were questioned about their openness to buying or living in a log-based residential building if the prices aligned with those of current market offerings. This approach was chosen to gauge people's attitudes towards living in wood-structured houses, ensuring the cost remained constant (Chart 3.11).

Chart 3.11. “If priced like other options, would you be willing to purchase or live in a log-based house in China?”

For detached homes, 328 respondents expressed interest, while 61 did not show interest, and 11 opted not to respond. In log-based apartment buildings, 324 participants had a positive reaction, 64 had an adverse reaction, and 11 did not respond. About 85% of the responses were positive across both housing types. Based on these responses, most people would be willing to purchase and live in a log-based house if the prices were comparable to the available options.

Survey participants were asked about their environmental concerns and whether they would opt for a log-based residence if it significantly reduced emissions during construction and use. According to Chart 3.12, of those who responded, 353 preferred living in a log house due to its considerable environmental benefits, while 34 were not in favour, and 13 did not answer. These results indicate that environmental considerations play a crucial role in shaping the housing preferences of many consumers in Northeast China.

Chart 3.12. “Would you be willing to consider a log house as a housing option if it significantly reduced carbon dioxide emissions related to construction and living?”

The survey featured a question aimed at gauging future trends, explicitly inquiring participants about their expectations regarding the growth of wood-based construction in their living areas in the coming years. Based on the feedback, 306 participants anticipated an uptick in wood-based construction within their localities, while 82 did not foresee an increase. Furthermore, 12 respondents opted out of answering this question, as illustrated in Chart 3.13.

Chart 3.13. "Do you see that wood-based construction will increase in your living area in the future?"

Reflecting on the survey results concerning market trends and purchasing intentions reveals predominantly positive outcomes, surpassing initial expectations. This suggests a notable shift in perceptions toward wood construction, likely influenced by growing environmental awareness or evolving aesthetic preferences. Many participants anticipate increased wood construction in their regions, indicating broader acceptance and enthusiasm for this method. While a more detailed investigation of the market trend is necessary for conclusive evidence, the initial impression appears promising.

3.3.4 Market Segment

Positioning log industry products in the luxury market segment is a calculated strategy. In China, where log houses are uncommon, they are perceived as a luxury that only the wealthiest can afford. Kontio has deliberately targeted its log products at this market. B2B Business Director Haipus emphasises the significant opportunity in China, noting, "In a country as vast as China, capturing even less than one per cent of the market can lead to substantial business" [94].

The survey findings reflect a similar perception among Chinese consumers, who predominantly regard log buildings as part of the luxury category. When asked if they viewed log houses as more costly to construct and live in compared to other housing options, about 70% agreed. In contrast, only a quarter of respondents thought building and residing in log houses wouldn't be more expensive than other homes (Chart 3.14).

Chart 3.14: "Do you think the construction and living costs of log houses are higher than those of other housing types?"

Market price comparisons provide insights into the positioning of log home prices within the larger real estate market of Northeast China. As of the end of 2023, figures from Finnish log construction companies indicate the cost of building a log house falls between 2,400 and 3,000 euros per square meter [97] [98]. In contrast, data from the Chinese Anjuke real estate app, dated late February 2024, shows that the price of new properties in Northeast China averages at approximately 1,700 euros per square meter in Shenyang, Liaoning, 1,410 euros in Harbin, Heilongjiang, and 1,150 euros in Changchun, Jilin.

Comparing the cost per square meter, log houses are roughly twice as expensive in cities like Shenyang and Harbin and nearly three times as costly as in Changchun. It's important to understand that listed prices for Finnish log houses exclude additional costs such as permits, zoning fees, or land acquisition. Consequently, Finland's actual cost per square meter often surpasses the figures quoted by Finnish log house manufacturers, varying by location.

Furthermore, standard prices in Finland see considerable adjustments with the start of international export of log construction expertise. Estimating the export costs for log homes is challenging without specific pricing and logistics information. However, it can be assumed that exporting these homes will lead to a significant price increase due to factors such as long transport distances, potential permits, tariffs, and logistical complexities. Especially if importing specialised construction labour and project management expertise from Finland becomes necessary, the overall costs are expected to surge.

Grasping the distinctions in land use and ownership between Finland and China is crucial for effective market segmentation. In Finland, people can buy land, obtain the necessary permits, and build homes. On the other hand, private land ownership in China is entirely restricted. Individuals may lease land to construct houses, but this procedure can be complex and lengthy, deterring many from pursuing it independently [99].

Given the differences in land use and ownership between countries, targeting the log construction market towards segments perceived as part of the luxury category is particularly strategic. Suitable areas for such market segmentation could include luxury residential projects for private owners and vacation destinations like ski resorts or holiday villages.

When examining the broader market segment, more giant hybrid log constructions in China could serve as modern public facilities, such as schools, concert halls, and cultural centres. These structures could utilise log construction's unique aesthetic and ecological benefits, positioning themselves as pioneers of innovative building technology. Such environments present a chance to highlight log construction's luxurious and inventive features, making the most of its distinct attributes.

3.4 SWOT Analysis

The SWOT analysis is a strategic framework widely used by various organisations, including businesses, government agencies, and associations. This analysis comprises four key components: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. Internal factors, such as strengths and weaknesses, offer deep insights into an organisation's internal workings. In contrast, external factors, opportunities and threats focus on assessing the external operational environment [105].

In this research, it is specifically applied to explore and discuss the opportunities and challenges as part of the final analysis for log construction in the Northeast China market area. This SWOT analysis aims to synthesise and summarise the significant insights from previous research and the information acquired in this study. The goal is to introduce new perspectives and enhance the understanding of the region's unique characteristics related to log-based building.

3.4.1 Strengths

The undeniable strength of wood construction in modern building practices lies in its ecological benefits. As previously noted in this study, the global construction industry is increasingly shifting towards sustainable and environmentally friendly practices, significantly benefiting the wood-based construction market. This transition is not merely a fleeting trend. Still, it marks a fundamental shift, redefining the industry's focus on sustainability—innovations in green construction utilising wood position the timber industry as a key player in global market entries.

In China, the growing interest in wooden construction can be seen from the various public projects undertaken in recent years, reflecting a nationwide willingness to incorporate sustainable building practices into their repertoire. The country's commitment to environmental initiatives is expected to extend across all its industrial sectors [107]. This trend underscores the increasing potential for wood-based construction, indicating a promising future for the industry.

Survey research in Northeast China has uncovered a highly favourable brand image for Finnish log construction, which is esteemed for its aesthetic appeal, desirability for living, and ecological and health advantages. The region's call for sustainable construction methods is propelled by increasing awareness of environmental issues and a commitment to health-conscious living. Based on the survey results, it can be cautiously estimated that most consumers would be willing to purchase and reside in a log-based housing complex if they had the opportunity and financial means. This openness to eco-friendly and low-carbon options underscores a significant chance for Finnish log construction in Northeast China.

Chinese authorities are pushing for a change in construction practices to mitigate the environmental impact of prolonged construction times associated with reinforced concrete buildings, which significantly contribute to on-site noise and dust pollution. They advocate for industrialising the construction industry, emphasising the integration of prefabricated structures into traditional building methods. This strategy addresses environmental concerns and makes

construction more efficient [107].

The move towards the industrialisation of timber construction has led to the prefabrication of factory materials, streamlining the assembly process at construction sites. This approach speeds up the building of timber frames and increases efficiency by optimising the manufacturing environment. Furthermore, wooden structures are relatively lighter than concrete and steel, facilitating more accessible transportation to construction sites and enhancing the adaptability of timber construction in modern building practices.

From a construction engineering viewpoint, managing moisture in subtropical climates poses a significant challenge for wood construction. However, the climate of Northeast China, which closely mirrors the continental climate of Finland, offers an ideal environment for wood construction [108]. This climatic compatibility guarantees that buildings constructed using this method can endure the local conditions with appropriate maintenance, avoiding major technical issues or deviations from the performance standards seen in Finnish climates.

3.4.2 Weaknesses

One of the notable challenges within the current wood building landscape is tied to the regulatory environment overseeing timber construction in China. A significant hurdle for timber construction comes from the rigorous fire regulations [110]. These regulations are particularly impactful in the building codes governing taller wooden structures. Legislation enacted in 2017 sets a cap on the height of timber buildings at three stories, or 10 meters, without a sprinkler system. When residential buildings are outfitted with sprinkler systems, this limit increases to five stories [111]. This regulatory framework contrasts Finland's approach, where wooden structures can be constructed up to two stories without a sprinkler system and up to eight stories with one [112].

The lack of contemporary guidelines and regulations for timber construction [110] markedly impedes its adoption and growth. Wood's relatively rare utilisation as a building material in China,

especially when compared with conventional steel and concrete methods, casts doubt on the present level of design expertise and knowledge within the realm of timber construction. A critical concern is the professional grasp of wood's characteristics and structural necessities. This deficiency in knowledge, coupled with elevated production and implementation expenses, strict guidelines, and restrictions on building height, renders timber construction an impractical option for numerous construction firms and real estate developers.

Access to materials for wood construction is a critical factor in the Chinese market. Although Northeast China boasts abundant forest reserves, their exploitation is limited by strict forest conservation policies [100] that restrict local timber's commercial use, impacting material sourcing strategies. Furthermore, the types of trees prevalent in Northeast China, such as maple, elm, tilia, ash, and Manchurian red pine [109], are not as conducive to log construction as the pine and spruce commonly used in Finnish construction. This discrepancy underscores the necessity for continuous research and adaptation to meet construction standards. The dependence on timber imports from countries like Finland or Russia introduces considerations related to availability, cost, and the complexities of international supply chains, which are especially significant in light of the fluctuating global economic landscape.

Entering the Chinese market successfully demands a deep understanding of its local business landscape beyond just the basics. This landscape's heart is *guanxi*, or interpersonal relationships, crucial for business growth and success within China. Navigating these relationships' intricate dynamics is essential for domestic and international companies. With China's business environment evolving rapidly, the importance of *guanxi* has never been more critical [113].

Interview data suggests that the Finnish log industry might face challenges due to its limited presence and understanding of the Chinese market. Trying to penetrate this market without strong *guanxi* or a comprehensive grasp of its complexities could pose substantial risks. Even minor misjudgements can result in severe strategic errors, endangering the future of companies seeking to establish a foothold in this profitable yet demanding market.

3.4.3 Opportunities

Timber construction must evolve from its traditional form to a new one to fully succeed in China's urban areas. These areas almost invariably favour high-rise structures, which limits the opportunities for conventional timber construction. Nonetheless, there is significant potential for timber construction within luxury suburban developments, where it is particularly well-suited for rural and resort settings. This includes upscale areas on the fringes of cities and leisure centres like ski resorts and vacation villages. Despite the challenges presented in urban centres, the real potential of timber construction lies in targeted growth areas where its ecological and aesthetic advantages are highly valued.

The log construction industry is experiencing significant evolution, marked by advancements enabling larger and taller wooden structures. These developments render Finnish log construction attractive for many projects, meeting the growing demand for sustainable building solutions. Particularly in China, structural timber is revived, driven by engineered wood innovations and fire safety enhancements [107]. This trend is in sync with a worldwide and local move towards eco-friendly construction practices, including a growing interest in taller timber buildings [110], signalling encouraging prospects for wood construction in the Chinese market.

The potential for the timber industry in China is vast, considering the market's size. Specifically in Northeast China, home to 94.6 million people according to the 2022 census, the opportunities are significant. Finland's population stood at approximately 5.5 million in 2022 [102], where the Finnish log construction industry primarily sources its customer base. Consequently, even a modest segment of the Northeast China market showing interest in Finnish log house products could translate into numerous projects in the future.

The economic landscape in China presents a promising outlook for the timber industry, particularly given the increasing wealth and spending capacity of Chinese consumers. This trend is poised to continue, with projections from Morgan Stanley indicating that Chinese consumer spending is

expected to double by 2030, fuelled by demographic changes such as family formation and retirement [103]. This surge in purchasing power is poised to significantly influence the real estate market, generating a demand for newer, cleaner, and more ecological housing options.

Increasing awareness and expertise in wood construction is essential to capitalise on this potential. One strategic approach could be through education, perhaps by forging partnerships with relevant universities. Such initiatives could offer long-term benefits, establishing a solid foundation for the region's proliferation of wood and log-based building practices. Therefore, Finnish companies must actively foster and share their knowledge through educational collaborations with Chinese institutions [107] [108].

While products from the Finnish log industry have been well-received, continuous innovation and adaptation are necessary to meet the unique environmental and cultural demands of Northeast China. Undertaking such initiatives is vital to enhancing the compatibility of Finnish log construction products with the region's specific requirements. Introducing new, innovative solutions that integrate the high-quality standards of Finnish log construction with sustainable development principles and local architectural traditions highlights the strengths and possibilities for Finnish log construction in Northeast China.

3.4.4 Threats

Timber construction presents substantial opportunities and challenges requiring meticulous analysis before market entry. A pivotal issue is the uncertainty surrounding market demand. While initial data might suggest robust demand, verifying the consistency and reliability of this demand is essential before making any forward strides.

Rushing into the market, particularly during economic downturns, could lead to adverse effects, endangering the company's survival. Thus, it is imperative for manufacturers of timber houses eyeing the Northeast China market to undertake comprehensive market research, perform thorough

risk analyses, and conduct detailed customer assessments to ensure informed decision-making and strategic planning.

Furthermore, the lack of clarity in local legislation and building regulations poses a substantial risk to timber construction companies in Northeast China. The risk that wood construction may not be widely accepted or adequately regulated introduces uncertainties and operational hurdles stemming from outdated or absent building codes and permit processes. In particular, the lack of specific standards for building safety and durability, or ambiguous enforcement of such standards, could subject companies to legal and liability risks.

Introducing log houses to the market, especially in regions unfamiliar with Finnish building techniques, carries significant risks due to the limited local experience with log construction. Deficiencies or construction errors during the building process could lead to disastrous outcomes from the perspective of the final product. A substandard final product can swiftly undermine the brand's value and tarnish the company's reputation. Additionally, consumer perceptions of defects and issues with the product could severely hinder marketing efforts and reduce its appeal, posing a critical threat to the success of a new product in the market.

These challenges are exacerbated by a scarcity of skilled labour and expertise in timber construction within the region, which hinders recruiting and training competent personnel. The struggle to guarantee high-quality craftsmanship might impact the safety and longevity of the structures. Furthermore, construction costs could escalate if labour is sourced from other areas, such as Finland. Consequently, housing prices may rise, further complicating the company's efforts to enter the market and sustain its presence effectively.

The existence of well-established companies in the industry presents a notable barrier for new entrants aspiring to introduce timber construction. Yet, a potentially more significant risk may emerge from innovations within the traditional building materials sector. The dominant use of concrete and steel in China and the introduction of new, environmentally friendly alternatives to

these materials pose a substantial challenge to timber construction's competitive stance.

Betolar, a Finnish company, has developed a technique to convert industrial waste into low-carbon building concrete, cutting carbon dioxide emissions by up to 75% compared to conventional steel-concrete construction [114]. Similarly, Sweden's SSAB has achieved a breakthrough in producing fossil-free steel, eliminating fossil carbon dioxide emissions in its production process [115]. Similar advancements are being pursued globally, with the potential to supplant traditional concrete and steel in future construction endeavours.

While these innovations have excellent global significance, they could prove fatal for timber construction in China. Designers, companies, and regulatory authorities already acquainted with concrete and steel might consider transitioning to these novel materials a more straightforward option than navigating the complexities of timber construction. Such a shift could significantly threaten the viability of timber construction in China, potentially diminishing interest in timber-based projects if the environmental benefits of timber are matched or exceeded by these innovations in making traditional materials greener.

Chapter 4 Results and Discussion

This chapter examines the findings and implications of the study and succinctly integrates them as a whole. The results are analyzed in light of the data collected, providing insights into various aspects of the research topic. Additionally, recommendations for future research are proposed to explore opportunities for advancing timber construction in China.

4.1 Reflecting the Results of the Study

The Finnish log construction industry's situation in Northeast China reflects global trends and local challenges and opportunities. In Finland, log construction is a deep-rooted tradition, and with increasing demand abroad, many companies in this sector have expanded to international markets. However, these companies face a different scenario in Northeast China, where they must navigate various challenges.

Survey results offer insightful perspectives on local attitudes and opinions toward log construction. Most respondents are familiar with Finnish log houses, and their brand value is highly positive. The general public's confidence in timber construction's safety and health benefits establishes a solid foundation of trust for the future. Most people are willing to choose a more ecological form of living if given the opportunity, further suggesting a positive outlook on increasing timber construction in the future.

Most respondents perceive log buildings as a premium option, which aligns with the strategy of Finnish log companies to market their products as luxury items. At present, log and other wood-based constructions cannot compete on cost with traditional construction methods in China, resulting in wood-structured buildings being categorised as luxury products, mainly accessible to the wealthier segments of the population.

Integrating log buildings into China's urban landscape presents challenges, primarily due to their typically low-rise design and higher costs. Consequently, a more viable market for log construction is anticipated in areas outside city centres. Here, log homes could attract wealthier individuals seeking a retreat from urban life, offering them a unique and eco-friendly living option.

In China, log construction is already established through efforts of both Chinese and foreign companies. Therefore, it is crucial for Finnish companies to strategize how they can differentiate their log products in the market. One promising avenue for future development could be taller log buildings, an area Finnish companies are actively advancing towards broader adoption as a mainstream construction method.

Currently, log structures have the potential to serve as distinctive buildings for experience centres, such as ski resorts or holiday villages, enhancing the visitor experience with their unique charm and environmental advantages. Log construction is possible in public infrastructure projects like schools, kindergartens, cultural centres, and libraries. This approach could provide aesthetic and environmental benefits and create unique and inviting community spaces.

Establishing networks is crucial in Chinese commerce, and at present, many Finnish companies may have significant opportunities for enhancement in this domain. For Finnish businesses to thrive in the market, a substantial investment in forging and nurturing relationships is necessary. Additionally, these companies must recognise that building relationships are time-consuming and complex, contrasting with the often more straightforward nature of daily trade interactions among European entities.

One approach to accessing more information and knowledge about the Chinese market could be through various pilot projects, or by developing and promoting intergovernmental pilot projects where feasible. These initiatives could help increase the prevalence and awareness of log construction systematically between the two countries.

Building regulations and laws in China do not yet fully support wood construction. Despite this, the growing interest in the Chinese market indicates that changes are expected in the future, though these will take time to implement fully. Given China's rapid urbanisation and the high demand for building plots, it's crucial to incorporate essential safety regulations, such as fire safety, into high-rise wood construction. However, issues related to building safety and technical concerns should not be seen as insurmountable barriers, as many countries have successfully navigated safety and technical challenges in high-rise wood buildings.

In Northeast China, scarcity of wood and log construction expertise is a limiting factor. Consequently, companies venturing into log construction in this region must invest significantly in training their personnel to ensure successful and loss-free completion of building projects. Enhancing design and implementation skills through educational collaborations with Chinese universities could enable future professionals to specialise in wood construction.

The issue of raw materials is critical and significantly influences cost considerations. Currently, utilising Northeast China's forest reserves for the needs of timber construction is questionable, necessitating the import of raw materials, which is both costly and risky. Finding ways to develop log construction that simplifies the procurement of raw materials while maintaining the structure's integrity as close to the original as possible is of utmost importance.

Like all wood-based buildings in China, log construction challenges other construction forms and requires a significant commitment to research and development. This is a lengthy process, with the benefits taking considerable time. However, with persistent development efforts, the right legislative changes, and a shift in the visions of the Chinese construction industry, log construction could eventually find its place as one of the building forms in the future.

4.2 Future Research Suggestions

Exploring log construction within China opens various technical, legal, and commercial research opportunities. The lack of comprehensive research in this area provides a valuable chance to undertake thorough studies to broaden our understanding and bring innovative approaches to the industry.

Central to the challenges faced by the log construction sector in China is the complex network of construction regulations. Success in the Chinese market is deeply linked to a thorough grasp of the technical opportunities and limitations imposed by this regulatory framework. A concentrated examination of required legislative changes could illuminate ways to ease the path for log construction, thereby laying the groundwork for developing relevant safety and technical standards that adhere to local and global best practices.

Technological advancements within log construction herald a significant opportunity for innovation, potentially fundamentally transforming traditional construction methods. By developing new materials, manufacturing techniques, and construction processes, mainly aimed at overcoming fire safety and building height limitations, there's a chance to modernise log construction. This modernisation is crucial to align with contemporary building standards and meet consumer expectations, making it desirable and necessary for the industry's advancement.

Furthermore, the challenge of raw material availability and its associated costs pose a significant hurdle. The apparent scarcity of local forest resources designated for construction necessitates an in-depth examination of the feasibility of utilising local wood species and navigating the complexities of material imports. Such investigative efforts are crucial in identifying strategies to render log construction a more viable and sustainable practice within the Chinese market. Through comprehensive research, it's possible to uncover methods to leverage local resources effectively or to optimise the import process, thereby ensuring the sustainability and economic feasibility of log construction in China.

A detailed cost-benefit analysis is essential to understand how log construction can be more cost-effective in the long run compared to traditional building methods. This research should consider factors such as energy savings and lower maintenance costs associated with log buildings. Financial projections and forecasts that illustrate the payback period and potential economic benefits of investing in log construction would be valuable for stakeholders and investors.

Log construction's environmental impact and sustainability potential necessitate a thorough evaluation within the Chinese context. Although the ecological benefits of log construction are widely recognised in Finland, conducting a comprehensive assessment of its environmental footprint in China—from material sourcing to the energy efficiency of completed projects—is crucial. These analytical endeavours are essential to steer the development of log construction practices towards enhanced environmental sustainability in China.

The deficiency in wood and log construction expertise, especially in Northeast China, signals a significant gap. Investigating ways to develop local expertise, perhaps through collaborations with educational institutions, is critical for enhancing the sector's success and promoting sustainable regional development.

Equally critical is the analysis of consumer behaviour and demand. Although preliminary findings suggest a favourable reception towards Finnish log houses, there is a pressing need for a more nuanced exploration of consumer attitudes, preferences, and purchasing behaviours. Examining factors such as price sensitivity, brand perception, and potential barriers to purchase will provide strategic insights crucial for the effective marketing and positioning of log houses in Northeast China and potentially in broader markets.

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Appendix

有关中国东北地区的芬兰木屋问卷。

Survey about Finnish Log Houses in Northeast China.

这项调查旨在了解中国东北地区居民对该地区建造芬兰木屋的看法或期望。调查结果将作为研究生研究项目的一部分，重点关注与该地区芬兰木屋市场研究相关的内容。我们的目标是更深入地了解芬兰木屋在中国东北地区的适用性。感谢所有参与调查的人！

This survey aims to understand the perspectives of residents in Northeast China regarding the construction and desirability of Finnish log houses in the region. The survey results will be utilised as part of a graduate research project focusing on market research related to Finnish log houses in the Northeast Chinese context. The objective is to gain deeper insights into how Finnish log houses may fit within this region. Thank you to all survey participants!

Q1 您属于哪个年龄组？

Multiple Choice

	Choice	Totals
●	18 岁以下 (Under 18)	8
●	18-24	140
●	25-34	242
●	35-44	140

	Choice	Totals
●	45-54	18
●	55-64	5
●	65+	2

Responses 562 Answered 555 Unanswered 7

Q2 您住在哪个省份？

Multiple Choice

	Choice	Totals
●	辽宁省。(Liaoning.)	175
●	吉林省。(Jilin.)	91
●	黑龙江省。(Heilongjiang.)	134
●	内蒙古。(Inner Mongolia.)	34
●	以上所提都不是。(None of mentioned above.)	120

Responses 562 Answered 554 Unanswered 8

Q3 您听说过芬兰的木屋吗？

Multiple Choice

	Choice	Totals
●	是的。(Yes.)	421
●	不是。(No.)	117

Responses 562 **Answered** 538 **Unanswered** 24

Q4 您觉得图片中的木屋适合居住吗？

Multiple Choice

	Choice	Totals
●	是的。(Yes.)	512
●	不是。(No.)	29

Responses 562 **Answered** 541 **Unanswered** 21

Q5 您觉得图片中的基于木材的公寓楼吸引人吗？

Multiple Choice

	Choice	Totals
●	是的。(Yes.)	481
●	不是。(No.)	59

Responses 562 **Answered** 540 **Unanswered** 22

Q6 当价格与其他住房选择相似时，您是否愿意购买或居住在中国的木屋中？

Multiple Choice

	Choice	Totals
●	是的。(Yes.)	448
●	不是。(No.)	95

Responses 562 **Answered** 543 **Unanswered** 19

Q7 您愿意在中国居住在基于木材的公寓楼吗？

Multiple Choice

	Choice	Totals
●	是的。(Yes.)	438
●	不是。(No.)	103

Responses 562 **Answered** 541 **Unanswered** 21

Q8 您认为木屋是安全的居住选择吗？

Multiple Choice

	Choice	Totals
●	是的。(Yes.)	411
●	不是。(No.)	133

Responses 562 **Answered** 544 **Unanswered** 18

Q9 您认为木屋是一种健康的居住选择吗？

Multiple Choice

	Choice	Totals
●	是的。(Yes.)	492
●	不是。(No.)	51

Responses 562 **Answered** 543 **Unanswered** 19

Q10 如果木屋显著减少了与建筑和居住有关的二氧化碳排放，您是否愿意考虑木屋作为住房选择？

Multiple Choice

	Choice	Totals
●	是的。(Yes.)	494
●	不是。(No.)	47

Responses 562 **Answered** 541 **Unanswered** 21

Q11 您认为相比其他类型的住房，木屋的建造和居住费用更高吗？

Multiple Choice

Choice	Totals
● 是的。(Yes.)	379
● 不是。(No.)	157

Responses 562 Answered 536 Unanswered 26

Q12 您认为未来你所在的居住地区会增加木质建筑吗？

Multiple Choice

	Choice	Totals
●	是的。(Yes.)	410
●	不是。(No.)	133

Responses 562 **Answered** 543 **Unanswered** 19